

EVALUATION OF CHEMICAL COMPONENTS, ANTI-OXIDANT PROPERTIES, AND LETHAL TOXICITY OF ALKALOIDS EXTRACTED FROM ESPAND (*Peganum harmala*)

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ABSTRACT. *Peganum harmala* L. is a multipurpose medicinal plant frequently used for psychoactive recreational purposes. Harmaline, Harmine, Harmalol, Harmol, and Tetrahydroharmine were determined and quantified as the main b-carboline alkaloids in its extracts. Seeds and roots consisted of the greatest levels of alkaloids, while stems and leaves included low levels of alkaloids. This study aimed to investigate the chemical components, anti-oxidant properties, and lethal toxicity of alkaloids extracted from *P. harmala*. Accordingly, this plant was collected from Zahedan province (Iran) in spring, and methanolic extract of its seed and leaf was extracted by the Soxhlet method. Then, phytochemical analyses included identifying flavonoids and phenolic compounds, anti-oxidant test, FT-IR analysis, and HPLC analysis. Also, the test was conducted after orally administrating the three doses of the methanolic extract and Harmine to 54 male Wistar rats in three groups (n=6 per group). The results show that, although the anti-oxidant properties of methanolic extract of leaves are higher (because of the existence of flavonoids and phenolic compounds) than seeds, there is a higher amount of β -Carboline in seeds of the plant. The results showed that Harmine was toxic at a much lower dose than the seed extract, and the seed extract can be toxic in low doses than leaf extract.

Keywords: *Peganum harmala*, phenolic compounds, high-performance liquid chromatography, antioxidant

INTRODUCTION

Peganum harmala L. (*Zygophyllaceae*), is a well-known plant used in popular medicine [1]. Its habitat is semi-arid conditions and sandy soils, and it is distributed mainly in the Mediterranean region. Also, it is found in Central Asia, North Africa, and America as well as Australia [2]. *P. harmala*, so-called “Harmal” or “Espand”, is native to the steppe zones of semi-arid and pre-desert regions including Iran, especially Sistan and Baluchestan [3].

Phytochemical studies of *P. harmala* isolated various chemical ingredients, including alkaloids, steroids, flavonoids, anthraquinones, amino acids, and polysaccharides from its seeds, leaves, flowers, stems, and roots [4]. Alkaloids, mainly β -carbolines, including Harmine, Harmaline, Harmalol, Harmol, and Tetrahydroharmine, are among these

compounds. These are the substances playing a critical role in different biological activities and pharmacological properties of its seeds, including hypothermia [5], hallucinogen factor [6], anti-depressant [7], an inhibitor of the enzyme monoamine oxidase (MAO) [8], anti-bacterial, anti-fungal and anti-virus [9]. It can effectively treat dermatosis disease [10], its leaves are used as an antinociceptive [11]. However, it causes abortion in rats [12].

While many studies have evaluated the separation and identification of alkaloids, including Harmaline and Harmol [13, 14], it is necessary for researchers must carry out the studies in different fields such as pharmacology, toxicology along with analytical chemistry to develop a simple, effective, and sensitive analytical processes [15].

This study has aimed to extract and evaluate the alkaloid compounds of its leaves and seeds collected from Zahedan province (Iran). According to the fact that the percent of its effective compounds are changed by the growth location of the plant, it is essential to evaluate the anti-oxidant properties and lethal toxicity of *Peganum harmala* ethanol extract.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Plant collection

P. harmala was provided from an area five kilometers away from Zahedan city (Sistan and Baluchestan, Iran) in the late spring. The plant was verified in the Central Herbarium of Iran (TARI) and recorded with the number: 107208. After the plant was dried entirely at room temperature, the seeds were divided.

Plant material extraction

To extract the plant organs (leaves and seeds), according to an earlier reported procedure with some modifications [16], 100 g of the plant was firstly chopped in a thimble and then in the middle hole of the Soxhlet extractor. Next, 500 ml of methanol solution (80%) was included. This procedure lasted for 3 to 4 h. After completing the extraction process, the extract was collected from the extraction chamber and stored in a refrigerator until use.

Extraction and identification of total alkaloids

The extraction and identification of alkaloids have become routine methods in the laboratory [17]. 5 ml of sodium carbonate (5%) was added to the dried plant powder (1 g) and was placed at the ambient temperature of the laboratory for 24h. Then, 10mL of ethanol (85%) was added and placed in the water bath (60 °C). The supernatant was filtered, and to the rest, 10ml of ethanol (85%) was added. Again, it was placed in the water bath (60 °C) for 15 min. The extraction process was repeated three times. Finally, the solvents were mixed. Depositions were separated from alcohol solution by centrifuging at 3000 rpm for 10 min. Then, the alcohol solution was poured into the beaker and evaporated at 50 °C. The dish wall was washed with 10 ml of Sulfuric acid (5%) and 10 ml of diethyl ether in a water bath (60 °C). The extract was separated from a lower acidic phase. The alkaline solvent of chloroform was added in the same volume, and a lower chloroform phase was gathered. This procedure was repeated three times. Again, the chloroform (with the same volume as the total volume of the lower chloroform phase) was added, and the lower chloroform phase was separated. Next, the collected

chloroform phase was evaporated at a low temperature. Finally, the dish wall was washed with 5 ml of methanol, and extracted alkaloids were prepared for qualitative and quantitative analyses. Also, secondary metabolites include alkaloids, anthocyanin, flavonoid, tannin, and anthraquinones; each of them has its way of identification. To detect these metabolites, laboratory methods were used [18].

Extraction analysis

The Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) (WQF-510 FT-IR Spectrometer, china), high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) (KNAUER, Germany) with C18 column; mobile phase (isopropyl alcohol: acetonitrile: water: formic acid [100: 100: 300: 3]), 1 ml/min flow rate, 330 nm wavelength were used to analyze the extract. Finally, the chromatograms were monitored.

DPPH-scavenging capacity assay

The DPPH (2,2-Diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl) method was used to study the anti-oxidant activity of extraction. The half-inhibitory concentration values (IC₅₀) were evaluated. The absorbance of extraction at 517 nm was assessed with UV-visible spectrophotometer (Hitachi, Japan) [19]. The percentage of free radical scavenging activity was identified through the difference in absorbance of DPPH between groups.

Assay of lethal dose (LD50)

Afterward, the extract materials were weighted to prepare the stock solution. Then, three doses of this solution (mg/kg body weight) (Table 1) were made up for the present study. Doses were selected logarithmically, and LD₅₀ was identified by behavioral, pharmacological studies of the extract [20, 21] with some modifications. In the experimental study, 54 male Wistar rats (250–300 g) were kept under laboratory conditions (a 12/12 h light/dark cycle, 21–23 °C, the humidity of 40%–70%, free access to water, and standard food). They were randomly divided into 3 groups (n=6), and drugs were administered by gavage. All animal tests corresponded to the ethical standard and guidelines for animal experiments of the Islamic Azad University of Tehran, Science and Research Branch, Tehran, Iran (IR.IAU.SRB.REC.1396.37).

Table 1. Administration of different doses of *Peganum harmala* ethanol extract and Harmine.

Drug dose (mg/kg B.W)	Groups (n=6)		
	1	2	3
Harmine (Sigma)	150	75	15
Methanolic extract of Seed	3.3	1.65	0.75
Methanolic extract of Leaf	10	5	1

Statistical analysis

All procedures were similarly repeated 3 times. Also, data were presented as mean ± standard deviation. SPSS 20.0 (SPSS Inc., Chicago, USA) and GraphPad Prism 5 (Prism, GraphPad Software, San Diego, CA) were used to analyze data. T-Test was selected for the analyses of differences between groups. P<0.05 was statistically significant.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Phytochemical analysis of the methanolic extract

As shown in Table 2, the methanolic extracts of seeds and leaves are 29.7% and 31.7%, respectively. The IC₅₀ for seeds was 122.1, for leaf was 200, and total phenolic compounds (mg GAE/mg) for seeds were 30.46, and for leaf 32.84. Also, total flavonoids (mg QE/mg extract) were 16.63 for seeds and 25.84 for leaf. The total alkaloids for seeds were about 7%, their Harmine content is 2.93%, and Harmaline is 3.8%, and the amounts of Harmane and Harmol and Harmalol are negligible at 0.02%. The total leaf alkaloid was about 0.2%, with the content of Harmine 0.055%, Harmaline 0.05%, and Harmane and Harmol and Harmalol are about 0.02%.

Table 2. Active ingredients of the methanolic extract of the seeds and leaf of *P. harmala*.

Bioactive compound of the extract	Extraction percentage (%)	Total alkaloids (%)					Antioxidant		Total phenolic contents (mg GAE/mg extract) at 200 mg/ml	Total flavonoids contents (mg QE/mg extract)
		Harmine	Harmaline	Harmane	Harmol	Harmalol	IC ₅₀	Scavenger (%)		
Seed	29.7	2.93	3.8	0.029	0.02	0.120	122.1	68.9	30.46	16.63
Leaf	31.7	0.055	0.05	0.011	---	0.026	>200	34.7	32.84	25.84

The chromatogram at 330 nm illustrated a thorough resolution of all peaks by HPLC (Fig. 1). Based on the findings, 150 mg of the extract consisted of 6.5 mg of the Harmine. By FTIR, Harmine can be determined as the main constituent in samples extracted from the seeds and leaves. The absorbance of the *P. harmala* relative to Harmine standard at the frequency regions of 4500–500 cm⁻¹ has been shown in Fig. 2. The spectrum of *P. harmala* corresponded to Harmine standard. The absorption of extract at different wavenumbers of 1072, 1237, 1455, 1624, 3072 was related to various functional groups such as (C-H), (C=O), (C=N), (O-CH₃), and (C-N), respectively.

Comparing the alkaloid to the Harmine indicated four intense bands at 3448, 2926, 1653, 1385 along with 1060 cm⁻¹ (Fig. 2). The band at 3448 cm⁻¹ was assigned to the surface O-H, and N-H stretches. The bands at 2926 were associated with C-H stretches of methylene groups on the surface. The bands at 1653 cm⁻¹ may be attributed to C=C or C=N stretching frequencies. The bands at 1060 were related to C=O stretches.

Fig. 1. Chemical components in the methanolic extract of the leaf (a) and seed (b) were analyzed by HPLC.

Fig. 2. The Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy spectra of *P. harmala* extract of seed (red), leaf (blue), and Harmine (green).

Fig. 3. Diagram of anti-oxidant analysis or DPPH of the methanolic extract of the leaf (a) and seed (b).

Anti-oxidant properties analysis and lethal toxicity

The DPPH method is frequently used to measure and screen the anti-oxidant activity of substances in vitro. There are several preferences for the method, including simple

operation, high sensitivity, and good reproducibility. The 50% radical scavenging activity (IC_{50}) is the antioxidant concentration by decreasing the DPPH concentration to 50%. When the IC_{50} decreases, the free radical scavenging capacity of the anti-oxidant becomes stronger; when the IC_{50} increases, the scavenging activity becomes weaker. The IC_{50} of seed extract is 68.9%, and the IC_{50} of leaf extract is 34.7% (Table 2, Fig. 3).

In the case of Harmine, after the highest dose of the drug was administrated to the animals (150 mg/kg Harmine), 100% of the population died. At the 75 mg/kg dose of Harmine, only 50% of the population died, and all remaining population also died after 72 hours. Administration of 15 mg/kg of Harmine lasted for a week, and the animals survived. In the case of seed extract, a 3.3 mg/kg dose was determined toxic, and 100% of the population died. In a 1.65 mg/kg dose, the very severe psychoactive effects of the extract disappeared, and eventually the animal died. At a 0.75 mg/kg dose, the animals survived. In the case of leaf extract, 10 and 5 mg/kg doses were considered toxic doses, and 100% of the population died. At the 1 mg/kg dose and below, the animal survived.

Natural products and medicinal plants become major sources of new active compounds being main molecules in recent medical preparations [22]. Researches on the chemical compositions of the extracts illustrate effective compounds, including beta-carboline and quinazoline alkaloids. Though, Harmaline along with Harmine is the most influential alkaloids commonly causing their useful influences. Several researches indicate that other alkaloids in this plant play a role in its pharmacologic impacts [22]. It has also been shown that the percentage of these effective compounds varies according to the place of growth of this plant, so the chemical composition of this plant is different in China, Europe, and the Middle East [14].

The research by Pandey et al., in the initial phytochemical screening of ethanolic, aqueous, and diethyl ether extracts of *P. harmala* showed that compounds such as flavonoids, alkaloids, tannins, triterpenes, sterols, anthraquinones, coumarins, and volatile oils are present in this plant [23]. This study corresponds to the current research.

In the study by Edziri et al., the phenolic content in its aerial part is more than its leaves [24]. According to the current study, the methanol extract illustrated the greatest number of polyphenols in the seeds. Differences in polarity of the anti-oxidative components may demonstrate the reason for the difference in extraction yield and anti-oxidant activity of the extracts. The solubility of phenolic compounds is controlled by the solution used and the degree of polymerization of phenolics. The correlation level between the phenolic content and anti-oxidant activity of the plant organs is a compelling dimension supporting the hypothesis that the former compounds precisely result in anti-oxidant activity [21, 25].

The research of quantitative assessment of alkaloids indicated the maximum percentage in the seeds, fruits, and roots determined as the source of final synthesis products [26]. The study by Herraiz et al., shows that β -Carbolines aggregate in seed and root, while their small amount exists in leaves, and stems and there is no β -Carboline in the flowers. The β -Carboline concentration is high in seeds and roots, so the concentration of Harmine and Harmaline is over 10%. There is a different molecular profile of alkaloids in the plant, so Harmane (2.0% w/w) and Harmol (1.4% w/w) exist in roots. Harmine, as well as Harmaline, are found in seeds. Harmaline is found in seeds, but Harmol is found in roots and stems [8]. Also, Harmalol is found in fruits and seeds. There is a small amount of Tetrahydroharmine in seeds; but there are no β -Carboline and Harmane (1-methyl-beta-carboline) in seeds. It is noteworthy that the latter study is consistent with the current study showing that harmane exists in the seeds (although tiny).

CONCLUSION

The phytochemical study showed that great bioactive chemical compositions in various extracts of this plant. When compared to leaves, seeds have the highest rate of alkaloids. The studied plant may be a potential source of effective medicines. Nevertheless, additional researches should be done to isolate the pure active principal from the crude plant extracts to develop appropriate treatment.

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Conflict of Interest. “The authors declared that there is no conflict of interest.”

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